

HILFER HOSILASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI.

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ABSTRACT

Hilfer ma’nosida kasr tartibli hosila qatnashgan tenglamalar o’rganilib, qaralayotgan tenglamaning elliptik qismi o’z-o’ziga qo’shma, musbat aniqlangan ixtiyoriy operatoridan iborat. O’rganilayotgan masalani yechish uchun o’zgaruvchilarni ajratish usulidan foydalaniladi..

Hilfer hosilasi

Hilfer ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila Reiman – Liuvell ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila va Caputo ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilalarning umumiy holi hisoblanadi. Shuning uchun yuqorida Reiman – Liuvell ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila va Caputo ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilalar haqida ma’lumotlar keltirdim. Endi Hilfer ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila va tenglamalar haqida ma’lumotlar keltiraman.

Ta’rif. Ushbu

$$D^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) = I^{\beta(n-\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} I^{(1-\beta)(1-\alpha)} f(t) \quad (1)$$

ko’rinishdagi tenglikka Hilfer ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila deyiladi. Bu yerda $n-1 < \alpha < n$, $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$ oraliqlardagi sonlar.

Agar $\beta = 0$ va $n-1 < \alpha < n$ bo’lsa (1) tenglik quyidagi ko’rinishga keladi:

$$D^\alpha f(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} I^{(n-\alpha)} f(t) \quad (2)$$

ya’ni, bu biz bilgan Reiman – Liuvell ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila hisoblanadi. $\beta = 1$ va $n-1 < \alpha < n$ bo’lganda esa

$${}^C D^\alpha f(t) = I^{(n-\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} f(t) \quad (3)$$

Caputo ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilaga kelar ekan. Demak, yuqorida aytganimizdek Hilfer ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila Reiman – Liuvell va Caputo ma’nosidagi kasr tartibli hosilalarning umumiy holi ekan.

Hilfer hosilasi qatnashan differensial tenglamalar.

Hilfer ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila qatnashgan differensial tenglamalar juda ham ko'p bo'lib ulardan ba'zilarini ko'rsatamiz.

Lemma 1. Agar $\mu > n - 1$ bo'lsa u holda quyidagi tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$D^{\alpha, \beta} t^{\mu} = \frac{\Gamma(\mu + 1)}{\Gamma(\mu + 1 - \alpha)} t^{\mu - \alpha} \quad (4)$$

Isbot. $\mu > n - 1$ bo'lsin. (2.1) tenglikdan m vaqtda farq qilsin

$$\frac{d^n}{dt^n} I^{\delta} t^{\mu} = \frac{\Gamma(\mu + 1)}{\Gamma(\mu + 1 + \delta)} (\mu + \delta) \dots (\mu + \delta - n) t^{\mu + \delta - n}. \quad (5)$$

Endi Gamma funksiyaning $\Gamma(z + 1) = z\Gamma(z)$ xossasidan foydalanamiz.

$$\Gamma(\mu + \delta + 1) = (\mu + \delta) \cdot (\mu + \delta - 1) \dots (\mu + \delta - n + 1) \Gamma(\mu + \delta - n + 1).$$

Endi yuqoridagi tenglikni (2.3.5) ga qo'llaymiz u holda biz quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\frac{d^n}{dt^n} I^{\delta} t^{\mu} = \frac{\Gamma(\mu + 1)}{\Gamma(\mu + \delta - n + 1)} t^{\mu + \delta - n} \quad (6)$$

Boshqa tomondan

$$I^{\beta(n - \alpha)} t^{\mu + \delta - n} = \frac{\Gamma(\mu + \delta + 1 - n)}{\Gamma(\mu + \delta - n + 1 + \beta(n - \alpha))} t^{\mu + \delta - n + \beta(n - \alpha)}, \quad (7)$$

va

$$\delta + \beta(n - \alpha) = (1 - \beta)(n - \alpha) + \beta(n - \alpha) = n - \alpha,$$

Bundan biz quyidagiga erishamiz

$$D^{\alpha, \beta} t^{\mu} = \frac{\Gamma(\mu + 1)}{\Gamma(\mu + 1 - \alpha)} t^{\mu - \alpha}$$

tasdiq isbotlandi.

Ta'rif. (Kasr tartibli hosilaning limit nuqtasi haqida). $-\infty < a < +\infty$ uchun kasr tartibli hosilaning darajalari $0 < \alpha < 1$ va $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$ bo'lganda $f(x)$ a nuqtadagi limiti deb quyidagi tenglikka aytiladi

$$D^{\alpha, \beta} f(a) = \pm \lim_{x \rightarrow a^{\pm}} D_{a^{\pm}}^{\alpha, \beta} f(x). \quad (8)$$

Tasdiq 1. $f : [a, A] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ bo'lsa $a < A < \infty$ oraliqda bo'lsin. Agar $(I_{a+}^{\beta} f)(a)$

$0 \leq \beta \leq 1 - \alpha$ bo'lsa

$$(D_{a+}^{\alpha, \mu} f)(x) = (D_{a+}^{\alpha, \lambda} f)(x) \quad (9)$$

qachonki $0 \leq \mu < \lambda < \frac{1 - \alpha - \beta}{1 - \alpha}$, va

$$(D_{a+}^{\alpha, \mu} f)(x) = \left(D_{a+}^{\alpha, (1-\alpha-\beta)/(1-\alpha)} f \right)(x) + \frac{\left(I_{a+}^{\beta} f \right)(a)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha-\beta)(x-a)^{\alpha+\beta}} \quad (10)$$

Barcha $\mu < \lambda = \frac{1-\alpha-\beta}{1-\alpha}$ lar uchun o'rinli bo'ladi.

Isbot.

$$\left(DI_{a+}^{1-\alpha} f \right)(x) = \frac{f(a)}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)(x-a)^{\alpha}} + \left(I_{a+}^{1-\alpha} Df \right)(x) \quad (11)$$

$g(x)$ ni vaqtinchalik quyidagicha belgilaymiz $g(x) = \left(I_{a+}^{(1-\lambda)(1-\alpha)} f \right)(x)$ va integral operatorning quyidagi xossasidan foydalanamiz $I^{\alpha} I^{\beta} = I^{\alpha+\beta}$.

$$\begin{aligned} (D_{a+}^{\alpha, \lambda} f)(x) &= \left(I_{a+}^{\lambda(1-\alpha)} DI_{a+}^{(1-\lambda)(1-\alpha)} f \right)(x) \\ &= \left(I_{a+}^{\mu(1-\alpha)} I_{a+}^{(\lambda-\mu)(1-\alpha)} Dg \right)(x) \\ &= I_{a+}^{\mu(1-\alpha)} \left(DI_{a+}^{(\lambda-\mu)(1-\alpha)} g \right)(x) - \frac{(x-a)^{(\lambda-\mu)(1-\alpha)-1}}{\Gamma((\lambda-\mu)(1-\alpha))} g(a) \\ &= (D_{a+}^{\alpha, \mu} f)(x) - \frac{(x-a)^{\lambda(1-\alpha)-1}}{\Gamma(\lambda(1-\alpha))} g(a). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Kasr tartibli integraldan foydalanamiz

$$I_{a+}^{\alpha} (x-a)^{\beta} = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha+\beta+1)} (x-a)^{\alpha+\beta} \quad (13)$$

$\lambda < \frac{1-\alpha-\beta}{1-\alpha}$ uchun (9) tenglik o'rinli chunki $g(a) = 0$ bo'ladi, va $\lambda = \frac{1-\alpha-\beta}{1-\alpha}$

bo'lganda esa (10) tenglik o'rinli.

Misol 1. $D_t^{\alpha, \beta}$ - Hilfer ma'nosida kasr tartibli hosilali, $I_{0+}^{1-\beta}$ - R-L kasr tartibli integrali. Bu yerda $0 < \alpha < 1$ va $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$ oraliqlarda bo'lsin. $f(t) \in C((0, \infty); \mathbb{H})$ va $\varphi \in \mathbb{H}$.

$$\begin{cases} D_t^{\alpha, \beta} T(t) + \lambda T(t) = f, \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow 0+} I_{0+}^{1-\beta} T(t) = \varphi. \end{cases}, \quad t > 0, \quad (14)$$

bu yerda $\varphi, f \in \mathbb{H}$. Koshi masalasi berilgan bo'lsin. Tenglamani yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$T(t) = \varphi t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda t^\alpha) + \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\lambda(t-\tau)^\alpha) f(\tau) d\tau. \quad (15)$$

Bizda manba funsiyasi $f(t)$ vaqtga bog'liq bo'lmasin. U holda (2.3.14) masala quyidagi masalaga aylanadi:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^{\alpha,\beta} T(t) + \lambda T(t) = f, \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} I_{0+}^{1-\beta} T(t) = \varphi. \end{cases} \quad t > 0, \quad (16)$$

(16) u holda masalani yechishda bizga Mittag - Liffler funksiya integrali yordam berdi. Ya'ni quyidagicha:

$$\int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\lambda(t-\tau)^\alpha) d\tau = t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha+1}(-\lambda t^\alpha). \quad (17)$$

(15) yechimdan foydalansak

$$\begin{aligned} T(t) &= \varphi t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda t^\alpha) + \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\lambda(t-\tau)^\alpha) f(\tau) d\tau \\ &= \varphi t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda t^\alpha) + f \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\lambda(t-\tau)^\alpha) d\tau = \\ &= \varphi t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda t^\alpha) + f t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha+1}(-\lambda t^\alpha). \\ T(t) &= \varphi t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda t^\alpha) + f t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha+1}(-\lambda t^\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Demak, (16) masalaning yechimi (18) ko'rinishida bo'lar ekan.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati:

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